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OBTAINING PATTERNED ADRAS KNITTING FABRIC ON A FLAT-TOOTHED MACHINE

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Annotatsiya: *Maqolada mahalliy milliy matolarimiz adras matosining rang barqarorlik xususiyatini yaxshilash maqsadida mahaliy adras shaklini yassi fang mashinasida glad va lastik to'qimasi asosida to'qilgan polakrilnitril ipidan trikotaj to'qimasiga tadqiq qilindi.*

Аннотация: *В статье с целью улучшения цветостойких свойств наших местных национальных тканей ткань адраса исследована местная форма адраса на плоскозубчатой машине для трикотажного полотна из полиакрилонитриловой пряжи, сотканной на основе гладкой и ластик ткани.*

Annotation: *In the article, in order to improve the color fastness properties of our local national fabrics, adras fabric, the local form of adras was studied on a flat-toothed machine for knitting fabric from polyacrylonitrile yarn woven on the basis of a smooth and elastic fabric.*

Kalit so'zlar: *trikotaj, mato, ip, chiziqli zichlik, akril, rang, milliy, deformatsiya, pishiqlik, cho'zilish.*

Knitwer, fabric, thread, linear density, acrylic, color, national, deformation, toughness, stretch. Трикотаж, ткань, поток, линейная плотность, lineynaya plotnost', akril, цвета, национальный, деформация, стойкость, протяжение.

Today, the demand for knitwear is growing and improving. This, of course, requires an increase in the range of new types of knitwear, the acquisition of new fabrics, and the production of competitive products [1].

The purpose of this study: knitted fabric can serve its owner for a long time, the appearance of adras in knitted fabric to expand the national range of top knitwear in late autumn to early spring, the reflection of nationalism in Uzbek design.

Adras fabric is the national fabric of the Uzbek people and is produced using the ABR method. The ABR yarn dyeing technique is very difficult, and the length of the yarn is 200-

300m. The libits are connected by two, and the frame is wrapped around the bench bars. The distance between the beams depends on the report template (1.4 - 2.25 m).

In ancient times, fabrics were dyed with vegetable dyes: royan, spark, pomegranate peel, egg, rosemary, nile (indigo), red. These paints do not dissolve either in the sun or in water. Natural dyes can be used to create a full range of colors. Not faded, not faded, not faded. These paints were used by folk craftsmen until the 70s of the XX century. Then they began to use aniline dyes. But they were ruined by not being fastened. Currently, they are treated with various chemicals. But pink (radomiri) and blue (bayon) could not be brought to perfection.

Today's rare clothes on adrasa fabric are resistant to water treatment, when their color fastness is not very good, because after washing the adrasa fabric, the adhesion between the silks becomes greater, the fabric loses its qualities, the colors do not overlap and do not stretch, but we have observed many such reasons. Thus, taking into account the above disadvantages, a knitted fabric was made in a knitted fabric with a copy of adras from a 35x2 rod yarn. The proposed mixing method consists of smooth surface and rubber, the purpose of which is to change the type of raw material, increase heat and shape-retaining properties, and ensure color stability. The mixed knitted fabric consisted of 2 layers and was obtained from polyacrylonitrile yarn using rubber and smooth fabrics. Local adr and patterned knitwear are differentiated from local adras, economic efficiency is increased, the use of polyacrylonitrile yarn has improved heat and shape stability, color fastness and wear resistance. The yarn used for research fabric is polyacryl nitrile synthetic yarn, which is one of the most widely used yarns in recent times.

Acrylic fibers are stronger than natural fibers (such as wool), so the product will last longer. Products made from high-quality acrylic yarn retain their shape well. Although acrylic is synthetic, it is pleasant to the human body and does not cause discomfort when wearing products made from it. In addition, since it is synthetic, it is not gnawed by moths, and acrylic, which is made from expensive natural fibers, is affordable and of high quality. Textile: Textile fiber is, as Dr. Bernard P. Korbman explains, “basically a type of acrylic plastic” [2].

Figure 1. Study example, knitted fabric with copy of adras

Figure 2. Obtaining adras patterned knitting fabric on a flat-toothed machine.

The characteristics of the physical and mechanical properties of knitted fabrics include: strength and relative elongation at break, relative elongation at low tensile strength, resistance to single and repeated stretching, resistance to shrinkage and abrasion, resistance to heat treatment [3].

Figure 3. Software on the flat knitting machine LXA - 252-12G

In the course of the study in the testing laboratory of the Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, the results of the physical and mechanical properties of the knitted fabric obtained on the LHA-252 machine based on adracopy were determined and the software was introduced (Fig. 3).

The results of physical and mechanical indicators for knitting.

Table 2.

Indicators	Options		By default
	knitwear		
Thread type, linear densities	Pan 35 tex x2		
% Of yarns in fabric	Akril 100 %		
Surface density of knitted fabric Ms (gr / m2)	387		
Knitting thickness T (mm)	1,89		
Dimensional density d (mg / cm3)	149		
Air permeability V (cm3 / cm2 · sec)	54,31		At least 40 for outerwear, 40 -100 GOST 31410-2009
Interruption force R (N)	along the length	344	At least 80N GOST 28554
	width	295	
Breakdown L (%)	along the length	56.8	6 N at 40% to 1 group, 40-100% to- 2 groups GOST 28554
	width	63.8	
Irreversible deformation en (%)	along the length	15.3	Not more than 15-20% GOST 28882
	width	19.8	
Back deformation eo (%)	along the length	86.5	
	width	83.9	
Friction resistance I (m / month)	38200		30-60 od-y 61-120 strong GOST 16486

The analysis of the physical and mechanical properties of the above-mentioned adras patterned knitted fabric showed that the research used Pan 35 tex x2 yarn for knitted fabric. 100% of the yarn in the fabric is acrylic. The surface density of the knitted fabric is 387 Ms (gr / m²), the knit thickness is 1.89T (mm), the bulk density is 149 d (mg / cm³), the tissue air permeability is 54.31 V (cm³ / cm²) · sec), 344 L (%) of the breaking strength, 295 R (N) of the width, 56.8 of the breaking length, 63.8 L (%) of the width, irreversible deformation length 15.3 eo, width 19.8 en (%), and reversible deformation neck 86.5, width 83.9 eo (%), friction resistance 38.200 I (m / ayl) showed indicators. As a result of the positive effect of the knitted fabric on air permeability, toughness, elongation and abrasion resistance, the shape of the knitted fabric for women's jackets, recommended for early spring and late autumn, is strengthened.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

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